

How to build a climate story

A practical guide

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REACH OUT
shaping climate resilient cities

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What is a climate story?

Climate stories use storytelling to communicate topics related to climate change. For many, climate change feels abstract, distant, and complex, making it difficult to inform, educate, or engage them in a way that truly connects. Storytelling makes it possible to communicate complex scientific data, model results, and knowledge to the intended audience. This approach helps to 'bridge the gap' between science and society.

Why tell a story?

Stories are a powerful and engaging way to communicate messages. Throughout history, people have used **storytelling** to share experiences and make sense of the world. Instead of merely presenting information, stories include human and relatable elements that connect with audiences on emotional and personal

levels. This connection fosters empathy and builds a shared understanding, making complex information easier to understand.

When to use a climate story?

Like all forms of communication, climate stories have their place and purpose. It is most effective as a tool for communicating messages, knowledge, or information in a way that transforms or influences the listener. Climate stories can deepen understanding, shift perspectives, or evoke emotional responses.

Storytelling is not an efficient approach for communicating detailed information, extensive amounts of data, or complex instructions. Instead, storytelling can be used as an introduction to a complex topic, sparking interest and enthusiasm that encourages the audience to explore the subject further.

Climate stories from six European cities are highlighted. Read the full stories on the [REACHOUT website](#).

This **practical guide** helps climate adaptation practitioners create their own climate stories. These stories can raise awareness about climate threats, share solutions, or inspire action. This guide was developed as part of the European research project [REACHOUT](#), which developed, evaluated, and refined a method for building climate stories.

The **spotlights** in this guide feature stories from six cities. However, the basic principles of storytelling can be used in almost any situation, as long as the goal is to connect personally and build shared understanding.

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Climate story development cycles

The approach is based on three interconnected development cycles. Along with developing the story itself, the *inspiration* for creating it serves as the starting point, while strategies for *sharing* the story are crucial to ensure its impact.

Cycle 1 - Plan: Set the goal of the story, decide on the main message, identify the audience, and find the best way to connect with them and the stakeholders.

Cycle 2 - Design: Make a storyboard that includes the storyline, visual style, characters, and mood of the story.

Cycle 3 - Create: Produce the content (media, graphics, data) and turn the story into a product.

Interconnectivity in the development cycles

Developing a climate story is not a linear process. While each cycle has a specific purpose, there is a high degree of interaction between them. For example, developing an infographic in the Create cycle may provide new insights, leading to changes in the narrative in the Design cycle, which could modify the core message in the Plan cycle. Be prepared to move back and forth between cycles, making modifications and adjustments.

Inspire

Storytelling connects on a personal and emotional level and therefore offers a powerful technique to initiate the transformation you want to achieve.

↳ **Understand the reason**

↳ **Interact with stakeholders**

Understand the reason

Before starting development, take time to understand the inspiration and motivation behind creating the climate story. As the future story owner, you or your organization have a reason for initiating this work and ideas about what you want to achieve. This sets an overall framework for the tone and style of the story.

A municipality may be inspired to develop a climate story for reasons like:

- Promoting the city's tree planting campaign
- Warning citizens about urban heat
- Encouraging bicycling

Awareness in Lillestrøm
Lillestrøm is developing a new regional plan for managing surface water due to intense rainfall. The climate story is intended to raise awareness in the community regarding the actions individuals can take to protect their property from water damage.

Climate plan in Athens
Athens has developed a Climate Action Plan (CAP). Communicating the goals and content of the CAP to the public was a clear inspiration and motivation for the city.

Interact with stakeholders

Involving stakeholders throughout the story development process is key to success. Collaborating with individuals or organizations with interest in the story allows them to contribute ideas, concepts, products, or solutions. This generates local ownership and support for the story.

There are various techniques to engage stakeholders, and the most effective one depends on the specific situation. As storytelling aims to make a personal and emotional connection, direct communication, such as meetings, interviews and discussions, is often the best approach. This helps to understand stakeholders' needs and expectations, develop a shared vision, and set shared goals. Direct communication also builds trust and credibility, and encourages involvement and creativity.

Language can be a challenge, and stakeholders often provide the best input when they can use their native language.

Stakeholder meeting in Gdynia
Gdynia hosted a meeting with stakeholders from the municipality to present a draft of their climate story. The session generated valuable feedback and inspired new ideas for shaping the story's direction. For example, participants emphasized the importance of educating citizens.

Tips

-
- » Start engaging stakeholders early, rather than waiting until later in the process. This helps build engagement and ownership.
 - » Be clear about the meeting's objectives and what stakeholders can influence.
 - » Use two-way communication (both talking and listening).
 - » Let the stakeholder input appropriately influence the outcomes. This involves balancing available resources for story development and incorporating fresh ideas.
 - » Keep stakeholders informed throughout the process, explaining why certain ideas were included or excluded.

Cycle 1 - Plan

This part of the process serves as an intention-setting and planning exercise, to establish the framework for developing the story.

- ↳ **Define the target audience**
- ↳ **Define the core message**
- ↳ **Set your goal**
- ↳ **Find interesting details**
- ↳ **Identify resources**
- ↳ **Choose your medium**
- ↳ **Plan the process**

Who do you want to reach?

Define the target audience

Define your target audience. Are you for example targeting citizens, politicians, policymakers, emergency services, young adults, business owners, or city planners? Do you want to reach all citizens, or a specific age group? Or are you targeting citizens with a specific interest such as gardening, hiking, or fishing? Climate stories are not “one size fits all”, and having a specific audience in mind will make it easier to develop your story, and to ensure its impact.

Vulnerable citizens in Logroño

Logroño selected children and the elderly as the target audience, with the ambition to communicate about heat hazards and how citizens can prepare themselves.

What is the core message you want to communicate?

Define the core message

In parallel with determining the target audience, define what it is that you want to communicate by establishing a short statement that summarizes the core message. Examples include: “Climate change is already happening in our city” or “Citizens need to depave their garden and this will have many benefits”. To guide this step, you may want to identify key climate data, knowledge, insights, plans or other information you want to share.

Combat increasing heat in Milan

The core message for Milan is ‘Heat waves will become more frequent and more extreme. Action is needed to mitigate the effects. Increasing green space in the city is a good solution to this and has additional benefits.’

What do you want to achieve with this message?

Set your goal

Define how you want the audience to react. Do you want to raise awareness? Or do you want people to develop new capacities, feel inspired, or take action? Clearly defining your core message and goals shapes your story’s direction and impact. If you want to warn for urban heat, your goal could be to:

- Educate citizens about self-help measures to keep cool
- Inspire children to use pools and fountains for play
- Encourage public support for more green spaces over parking
- Inform citizens about long-term climate projections.

Engaging citizens in Gdynia

Gdynia’s climate story has two goals:

1. Raise awareness among citizens on what the municipality is doing on adaptation.
2. Encourage citizens to join in adaptation action.

Tips

- » Revisit your goals regularly to check if your initial thoughts still hold throughout the development cycles or if you can make your original message more specific!
- » Start thinking about how you could monitor and evaluate progress towards reaching your goal (e.g. through surveys, interviews, observations, and determining whether an initial benchmark baseline is needed)

Find interesting details

Developing the story starts by collecting useful ingredients such as iconic locations and landmarks, ideas for characters, memorable events, personal anecdotes, or other components that resonate with the local community.

Local or cultural connections

Consider if there are any local personalities, artists, mascots, traditions, occasions, specific locations, or other references that the target audience would appreciate. Reflect on the local history, culture, stories, or humor that can be incorporated into the story to make it more relatable and engaging for your audience.

Emotional connections

Consider whether there are experiences and stories that the audience will relate to emotionally. Reflect on previous floods, heatwaves, or other relevant events that are a part of your audience's collective memory, fostering a deeper emotional connection to your story.

The owl of Athens

Athens uses the "Owl of Athens" as a character in its story to look ahead to the year 2030. The Owl is a symbol for wisdom and foresight, and has a strong connection to the city, originating from Greek Mythology.

Identify resources

Determine what (climate) data is available and whether you or your organization have media resources such as images, videos, historical archives, infographics, brochures, or publications. Spatial information can be a valuable addition to your story, for example to map climate data or show where measures have been implemented.

Plan, photos and maps in Lillestrøm

Lillestrøm had recently adopted the municipalities Climate Plan as a point of departure. Furthermore, historical photos and videos of past flood events were found in the archives, and the city also had a substantial GIS data set with relevant content.

Subsidies and tutorials in Gdynia

Gdynia had many subsidies for citizens available to act, as well as extensive information about possible measures and tutorials. This was identified as a relevant resource to include in its story. Through the story citizens have a clear overview and access to this information.

Tips

» This development cycle is about collecting inspiration and ideas! Do not restrict yourself or think too much about how this could translate into a story. The idea is to gather ideas and resources that will support you later when you need to develop a narrative.

Choose your medium

There are many ways to develop and present your climate story, each with its own unique strengths and weaknesses. It is important to choose a medium that is easy to share with your audience and that you and your team feel capable of using. Different types of media span traditional printed material to digital platforms, and the digital medium can be either an open-source tool or a licensed service. For instance, most climate stories spotlighted in this guide, were developed using the geospatial storytelling tool ArcGIS StoryMaps, which is a licensed service.

However, you can also use slides, make a video, or develop your own fanzine. You can even develop a custom online tool or website.

Animation video in Cork

Cork made an animation video together with a local artist to show how Cork has always been dealing with water challenges and how the city council makes efforts to address this.

Tips

- » Ensure that your climate story is accessible to your entire audience. For example, not everyone has access to technical tools or a computer. Consider offering offline content, such as printed materials to ensure everyone can engage with your story.
- » Choose the medium based on who you want to reach. For example, children might prefer a short video instead of a webpage with text.

Plan the process

Identify the stakeholders

Developing a climate story requires a well-managed co-creation process with stakeholders. These include the target audience, individuals, groups and organisations with relevant knowledge and skills to influence the story development, implementation and distribution.

Plan key steps

Co-creation requires interaction and activity, and this needs planning. Identify the activities needed (brainstorming ideas, collecting local knowledge, finding resources...), how these may be implemented (workshops, meetings, digital whiteboards, video meetings...), and include time for iterations and feedback cycles. Test new ideas and updates frequently with relevant stakeholders to keep the process agile and avoid stories that do not align with stakeholders' needs and inputs.

Link stakeholders to key steps

Select relevant stakeholders to engage in each key step; include key decision makers in early in the process. Clearly communicate with all stakeholders to manage expectations and ensure a productive development process. A small core development team (CD-team) to coordinate the process is ideal.

Iterative process in Milano

The CD-team: Two REACHOUT advisors and one city representative.

- *Kick-off*: CD-team brainstorming to develop building blocks for a story.
- *Draft narrative*: Local policymakers and CD-team in co-creation develop a story and additional building blocks.
- *Three development iterations*: Story matured through three cycles in the CD-team, incorporating stakeholder feedback in each cycle.

Cycle 2 – Design

This is the creative process where ideas are generated, and your story is crafted.

↳ **Outline the narrative**

↳ **Make a storyboard**

Outline the narrative

Narrative structure

Develop the outline of your story. This includes defining your main character(s) and building a story about them. Keep in mind your target audience, core message, and goal, and use the ingredients you have identified earlier, such as interesting details and ready resources. To assist you, consider using the narrative structure of 'The Hero's journey.' You may recognize this structure from fairytales such as Little Red Riding Hood, where the young girl is the hero of the story. While there are many possible narrative structures, this one is particularly effective for learning as well as its familiarity and emotional engagement, thus making it a good choice for building climate stories. The Hero's journey is about defining the following four components:

1. Setting the scene

Where and when does the story begin? What does this look like? Who is/are the main character(s)? And what does your audience need to know about the character(s)? Ensure that you make this specific, personal, and local, so that the audience can relate to it.

2. Trigger

The trigger is a change in the initial situation. Something intriguing happens or changes. The journey begins! The story is set into motion and the audience is compelled to find out what happens next. How can you capture the audience's interest and keep their attention?

3. Helpers and threats

Throughout the story the main character(s) encounters threats and helping hands. Think of hurdles and helping hands that influence the character's pursuit of their goal(s). This makes your story dynamic and interesting.

4. Take-away message

Determine how the story ends. What is the end-situation of the main character? It should always be different to the initial situation. What transformation has occurred? What lesson do you want the audience to take away? Is there a call to action?

A sweet young girl lives in a small house in the forest. Whenever she goes outside, she wears a little red riding hood that her grandmother made.

SETTING THE SCENE

The Owl of Athens takes you to the year 2030. Sophia is an elderly woman living in a small apartment in the city.

Her grandmother is sick. Her mother tells her to visit with fruit. She warns her: 'Stay on the path!'

TRIGGER

One august morning, she prepares to spend time with her grandchildren. Sophia turns on the news. Extreme heat is expected the coming days.

But she sees beautiful flowers and leaves the path to pick them.

A big wolf, however, sees her in the field of flowers - she is a little fresh treat to him. He eats her.

Sophia and her grandkids try to have a nice day, despite the heat. They go to the park to cool down.

HURDLES & HELPING HANDS

Luckily a hunter finds out, and rescues her from the wolf's belly.

On their way home they witness a man having a heat stroke.

A red cross worker explains what you can do to prevent a heat stroke.

A lesson from Little Red Riding hood is 'always listen to the advice of your parents'.

TAKE AWAY MESSAGES

The municipality and its inhabitants need to team up to take action to implement the city's Climate Action Plan. People need to become more aware of what they can do during a heatwave.

The illustration on the left page gives two examples of stories and their narrative components, one for the fairytale of Little Red Riding Hood and one for a climate themed story for the city of Athens.

At this stage, it is not yet about writing dialogues or crafting detailed scenes. You develop the general outline of the narrative elements, determine the beginning and the end of the story, and any transformation or change you would like to see. Developing the outline is a creative process. Brainstorm and collect ideas. You will encounter considerations like: Do you want the story to shock the audience or a story that promotes positive feelings? Do you want something playful or serious? Do you want to base the story on real people and events, or fiction? Explore different options and decide what is the best for your climate story. It will take some iterations of brainstorming

Tips

- » Don't do this on your own. Brainstorm with a group of diverse people to collect different ideas. This may be limited to the core development team but can also involve additional people depending on the expertise represented in your development team. Check if you are still engaging the right stakeholders as defined in the Plan cycle.
- » Check if your story ideas align with your target audience, goal, and core message as established in the Plan cycle.

What is the overall look and tone that you want to achieve?

How might the story unfold, scene by scene?

Make a storyboard

A storyboard is a visual representation of how your story progresses, scene by scene. You can elaborate your narrative into a storyboard in two steps. First, develop a map narrative. This is an overview that lays out the main scenes of the story. Use these keywords to describe each scene.

- **Setting:** Where/when does the scene take place? What does it look like?
- **Milestone:** What is happening in the scene?
- **Impact message:** What is the key point you want to tell with this scene?
- **Resources:** If any, what resources does this scene include? (e.g., climate data, adaptation plan).

Storyboard in Lillestrøm

Setting the scene

Water is the life of Lillestrøm. For everyone who lives and works in the city.

Add positive visuals of Lillestrøm and the water system.

Setting the scene

The history of Lillestrøm has been shaped by the Niteelva river, the saw mills and the surrounding water and rivers (Leira, Sagelva, Glomma).

Add positive visuals of the water history / saw mills of Lillestrøm.

Trigger

Add visuals of effects / impacts of floods / River flooding in Lillestrøm: the actual trigger in this story.

But the effects of climate change are turning water into a possible threat. The risk of floods, erosion and landslides is growing. An old friend is becoming a future foe.

Second, develop a visual representation for all scenes. For example, this can take the form of a simple collage, where you bring together initial ideas for text, character impressions, and ideas for figures, graphs, or videos. The storyboard also conveys the overall 'look and tone' of the story.

This means deciding on:

- a color palette and text fonts
- illustration, visual and graph styles
- dynamic versus static images
- using a personal viewpoint (I) or third person (narrator)

The visual layout of the story should be consistent from beginning to end.

Storyboard in Logroño

Javier and Maria				
Setting the scene: family at home				
Introduce characters Maria (12) and her brother Javier (16) Ordinary school kids	Logroño municipality	Trigger: family irritated in the morning due to heat.	Supporting data: Climate projections	Objective: teach ways to keep cool
At school. Learning about heat effects		Milestone: impacts on vulnerable persons		Resolution
Objective: teach about urban heat island effects	Objective: teach about impacts on vulnerable persons	Resources needed: produce social vulnerability map over city center.	Helpers: Emergency services	City plans and strategy to project public health

Taking the Logroño storyboard further by adding some visual elements and supporting ideas. Expand the scenes as resources and ideas become available.

Tips

- » Look around and be inspired by other visual products!
- » Consider aligning the style of the story to the visual identity of your organization.
- » Check if all relevant stakeholders were engaged as defined in the Plan cycle before moving forward to the Create cycle.
- » Check if your story ideas align with your target audience, goal, and core message as established in the Plan cycle.

Cycle 3 – Create

This is the more technical part of the process, where you transform the storyboard and narrative elements into text and implement them in your technical platform.

↳ **Develop the script**

↳ **Develop visuals**

How can you write a text that is suited for your target audience?

Develop the script

The storyboard scenes serve as a guide to outline the sequence of events, characters, and key actions in a story. Now, you can use these scenes to write the narrative text. Here are important points to keep in mind:

1. Write concise text

Convert the elements from the storyboard into descriptive text. Tailor the content to your audience, using an appropriate language level. Avoid jargon, use active writing and keep the text clear and straightforward.

2. Make it personal

Add depth by including the characters' motivations and emotions. Translate complex concepts to everyday experiences and examples familiar for the target audiences. Include local details and references.

Concise and easy text

For example, avoid: "The interaction between climate change and precipitation patterns is hypothesized to result in alterations within the water cycle, influencing hydrological processes. These shifts, driven by complex atmospheric factors, are expected to affect the distribution and variability of precipitation, though the extent and nature of these impacts remain uncertain".

Rather use: "Climate change causes more intense precipitation events. This influences the water cycle, which is the way the water moves across our planet."

Tips

- » If you have access to a communication or language specialist, have them critically review the text.
- » Check if you are still engaging the right stakeholders as defined in the Plan cycle.

How can you use visuals to balance text?

Develop visuals

The phrase “A picture is worth a thousand words” is well-known for good reason. Visuals strengthen your story by enhancing understanding, engagement, and emotional impact. They are an excellent way to translate and tailor climate data and tools because they simplify complex information, making it easier to understand and interpret. For your story, it is important to have a balance between text and visuals so that neither overwhelms the other. You can use many types of visuals.

Maps offer geographical context, helping the audience visualize locations and understand the spatial relationships between climate data, adaptation measures, and the surroundings.

Photographs evoke emotions and help the audience connect with characters and situations.

Infographics simplify complex concepts into easily understandable visuals that help the audience quickly understand details without lengthy explanations.

Graphs convert raw data into visual representations, making it easier to understand and interpret complex information. Graphs can help the audience quickly grasp patterns trends and comparisons.

Use **illustrations** to set a mood or emphasize aspects of the story. In particular, illustrations of the character(s) can bring the story alive. You can ask a local artist to make visuals for your story.

Use **videos** to highlight a concept, feature an interview, or set a scene.

Maps in Athens

Map showing the walking distance to cooling areas.

Infographics in Milan

An infographic can be used to communicate data in a more accessible and personal way. In this example, an infographic explaining that during Gaiia’s lifetime, the frequency of alarming heatwaves will increase (right), clearly communicates the graph-based presentation of data (left).

Illustrations in Logrono

This illustration is more vivid and easily remembered than a sentence stating ‘The main characters learned about climate change in class’

Visuals in Gdynia

Photo’s and maps can be combined into an attractive visual, for example to inspire citizens with the measures they can take in urban areas.

Tips

- » Ensure a consistent visual style that matches the tone and theme of your story.
- » When communicating scientific information, adjust your visuals to the level of your audience.
- » Use images of high quality.
- » AI is useful for developing placeholder images when you do not yet have access to suitable images.

Share

↳ Reach your target audience

↳ Measure impact

What media channels are best for reaching your target audience?

What does a “successful launch” mean to you?

Reach your target audience

Media campaign

Once you are satisfied with your climate story, you will want to make your audience aware that the story exists and motivate them to access and read it. An engaging media campaign, tailored towards the specific audience you want to reach is therefore recommended. A media campaign typically involves several key steps that mirror the first steps of the Strategy cycle of your climate story; identify your target audience, the core message, and the goal of the climate story. Further to these steps, a media campaign includes the selection of the media channels to be used (e.g. social media, TV, newspapers). For example, social media campaigns or events at schools are effective if youth are your target audience, while promoting your story on the radio or in the newspaper can be better for reaching older audiences.

Promotion in Lillestrøm

Lillestrøm wished to reach their citizens with the story, and especially adults. Lillestrøm promoted their story using digital totems in central parts of the city, where citizens could scan a QR-code to access the story with their phone. They also promoted the story in an interview in a local newspaper, and on their official website, Facebook- and LinkedIn-pages.

Launch strategies

As part of the media campaign, a climate story launch strategy should be prepared. This should include a timeline for when and where the climate story will be released, as well as securing the necessary ad space or time slots. The core development team should also consider how to introduce the climate story to the target audience, such as through teaser campaigns or in conjunction with a major event.

The REACHOUT project

The REACHOUT project has actively used social media platforms to generate interest and excitement for the launching of climate stories developed for the REACHOUT partners. These are effective tools for reaching a wide audience.

Tips

- » If you have access to communication specialists, it is a good idea to engage them in planning effective media campaigns.

How can you measure the impact of your climate story?

Measure impact

Monitoring tools can be used to measure the use of your climate story, and to subsequently assess the impact of your media campaigns. They are not an essential part of climate the story development, but can provide valuable information about the success of your story. Some examples of monitoring tools include:

- **Web analytics:** If your climate story is hosted online, these tools can count the number of visitors over time, and in some cases provide more information about their area of origin or how much time they spend reading your story. ArcGIS StoryMaps currently has built-in support for Google Analytics and Adobe Analytics, and other options exist for other digital platforms.

- **Surveys and interviews:** Digital surveys or questionnaires can be embedded in your online climate story. Alternatively, printed surveys can be distributed and completed at a stakeholder meeting, workshop, or other media campaign event. These can give you more specific feedback on your climate story. Interviews are a useful source of information if you want to gain a more in-depth understanding of how the story is experienced and evaluated by the target audience.

Remember to follow data regulations when storing user data, and to let users opt in to having their information stored (e.g. as defined in the European law on data protection: GDPR).

Tips

- » Consider the timing of your launch. Can you link it to a relevant event? For example, a story on the impacts of heatwaves will be most relevant during the summer.
- » Engage communication specialists to help you develop a launch strategy.
- » Consider where the audience will find out about the story, and how they will access it.

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